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Revisiting Alexis de Tocqueville's Civil Society Concept from a Political-Economic Perspective

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to re-examine the civil and political associations of Alexis de Tocqueville, who is seen as one of the founders of the concept of civil society in the modern sense. With a historical approach to Alexis de Tocqueville's conceptualization of civil society, it is claimed that there is a cleavage between his views on civil society then and civil society in the modern sense and by employing this historical perspective, the study aims to demonstrate the separation between political - civil associations and the state coincides with the distinction of the political and economic spheres. To make the paper's central argument clear, it is argued that the concept of civil society contributed to regulating the political sphere in the political-economic distinction created by capitalism. Through this regulation, it is claimed that the specific understanding of civil society was in harmony with the social conditions from which American capitalism emerged. The study argues that civil society cannot be seen as separate from the state, politics and economy by reading the civil society debates on the axis of Alexis de Tocqueville and capitalism.

Introduction: Problematizing Sources of Alexis de Tocqueville's Civil Society Concept

In contemporary understanding, different kinds of aspects and definitions have been attributed to civil society. These definitions cover the outside of family, market and state; all kinds of social actions run by individuals, groups, and legal or social institutions ranging from Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs)¹, religious organisations to online groupings without the need of any kind of legal or physical structure (Cooper, 2018: 4). In the existing literature definitions of the civil society vary so that there is no consensus on a single definition. However, it is not impossible to differentiate and categorise them based on different aspects. Those aspects basically, can be seen as an area of outside the state (Adloff, 2021: 151; African Development Bank, 2012: 6; van Rooy, 1998: 11), of public sphere (Blaney and Pasha, 1993: 6; Kohler-Koch and Quittkat, 2009: 14; Susen, 2020: 394; van Rooy, 1998: 21), of voluntary participation (African Development Bank, 2012: 6; Cohen and Arato, 1997: 19; Goldberg, 2001: 293; van Rooy, 1998: 15) and of relating civil society to democracy (Adler-Wollstein and Kohler-Koch, 2008: 198; Adloff, 2021: 152; Blaney and Pasha, 1993: 8; Cohen and Arato, 1997: 19; Delalieux, 2022: 628; Edwards, 2004: 4; Eikenberry and Kluver, 2004: 133;

¹ From now on, in order to emphasize the difference between a modern association and the associations that is mentioned in a tocquevillean way, the term 'NGOs' will be used to indicate the modern civil associations, while 'association' (with a lower case letter) will be use to indicate a tocquevillean association.

Ishkanian, 2007: 3; Kohler-Koch and Quittkat, 2009: 14; Richter, 2004: 64; Susen, 2020: 397). All these four basic aspects of civil society are connected and support each other, especially within the realm of democracy.

For Kohler-Koch and Quittkat (2009: 21), an understanding of civil society includes all of the civil society organisations, regardless of whether their intentions are social or economic, based on membership and thus creates a link between representative democracy via their members. For van Rooy (1998: 30), civil society does not include all the civil society organisations but only the ones working for democratic and developmental goals in an active way in their countries. According to Blaney and Pasha (1993: 8), civil society offers a perspective for democratisation, not as a goal but as a process. When civil society finds stability, it may contribute to the democratisation of both state and civil society itself and spread the rights. For Adloff (2021: 152) a developed civil society requires some democratic institutions as precondition for its existence like “representative government, competing political parties, regular elections, a secret ballot, universal suffrage, an independent judiciary, a free press, the freedom of association, independent educational institutions, private property, and the freedom of contract”.

According to Adler-Wollstein and Kohler-Koch (2008: 195–196), because of the two main roles of civil society, defending the political rights of citizens and securing good governance, it may find solutions for the problems of democracy. From a neo-Tocquevillian perspective², for Cohen and Arato (1997: 19), without a civil society, the democratic characteristics of the social and political institutions cannot be maintained, and because of this, civil society, which is based on egalitarian principles, inclusion and active participation, is vital for the reconstruction of democracy. From another neo-Tocquevillian understanding, civil society is a defence counter to the sovereignty of a particular group and is a barrier against anti-democratic forces (Edwards, 2004: 7–8).

Although an important part of the literature claims a positive correlation between civil society and democracy, there are also several literatures which take this relation from a critical point of view in touch with the economy and capitalism. For Wood (1990: 61), an early definition of civil society is an area of human relations that is differentiated from the state, the public and the private. It is more about a place for economic relations, an area of the market, a sphere of production and exchange. The emphasis on the economy is important for Wood because she addresses a modern means of civil society with reference to the necessity of a separation of an autonomous economic sphere from a political sphere. Civil society demands the construction of the individual with the capitalist division of labour in two ways: firstly, the recognition of legal persons depends on the expansion of the division of labour. Secondly, due to an expanding division of labour, people are constructed as needing each other (Blaney and Pasha, 1993: 8). So, only in a capitalist economy, where the economic and political spheres are fully divided but also related, can civil society be conceived. For a civil society, a central stabilisation of the system of rights –and its legal and institutional structure– is essential. This stabilisation is important because through the rights, people become individuals and certain groups as corporate entities (Blaney and Pasha, 1993: 6–7).

A concept of civil society that includes many different aspects, from household to capitalist mode of organisation, shows the feature of changing meaning through time, but also hides its vast relationship underneath those aspects. When the capitalist society is reduced to a mere set of conceptual institutions and social relations, it might be hard to see its systemic power and coercive nature. By conceptualising capitalist structures as just one part of a broader, fragmented social reality, the totalizing logic and coercive dynamics of capitalism become invisible. When capitalism is presented this way, as equivalent to households or voluntary associations, the underlying

² The term, Neo-Tocquevillian perspective is refer to some of Tocqueville's interpreters' usage this term as a way the idea that democratic principles can be taught by using the instructive capacity of civil society.

expansionary drive, its pervasive influence, and the power structures inherent in it are effectively neglected from consideration (Wood, 1990: 65).

This reductionist view, which treats capitalism as one institution among many, risks making its systemic and oppressive features less apparent. It shifts the focus away from capitalism's ability to shape society as a whole, its capacity to expand and penetrate all aspects of social life, and its coercive impact on individuals and communities. As a result, such an understanding detaches capitalism from its true nature as a driving force that affects every sphere of human existence, thus neutralising the critique of capitalism that emphasises its all-encompassing, dynamic, and coercive power.

From a historical point of view, the development of the West cannot be seen as just the rise of individuality, the rule of law, or the progress of freedom and power from "below." Instead, the autonomy of "civil society" takes on a different meaning. As the state assumes more roles in everyday life, as the division of labor becomes increasingly complex, and as demands for the redistribution of wealth increase in the society, a notion of civil society becomes essential (Kaldor, 2011: 19). The changes, while seemingly positive, also led to new forms of exploitation and domination, such as personal dependence, the privatization of surplus extraction, and the transfer of old forms of oppression from the state to society—essentially shifting power from the state to private property. This division of labour between the state and society laid the groundwork for capitalism, which separated private gain from public responsibility. Capitalism represents both the culmination of this long process and a qualitative break in history, emerging in England under specific conditions. Modern social classes, which are organised by agriculture, manufacture, and trade, replaced the old ones with the existence of three modern components of production: land, labour, and capital (Ehrenberg, 2017: 119). It marks not only a transformation in social power and a new division between the state, private property, and class, but also the creation of a new form of coercion: the market. The market becomes not just a space for opportunity and choice, but a force of compulsion and discipline, controlling all human activities and relationships (Wood, 1990: 71).

These changes also find their place in the field of politics. For Wood (1990: 72), after the rise of the masses in politics, it became harder for the ruling classes to outright reject democracy; the meaning of democracy started to focus more on procedural or formal aspects rather than its social implications. In other words, the concept of democracy was "domesticated," making it easier for the dominant classes to claim they supported democratic values without threatening their own power or in other words, making democracy suitable for market conditions.

For Adloff (2021: 150), there can be a relation between civil society and economy, such that the economy and the capitalist mode of production can be reorganised in accordance with the democratic principles of civil society, and thus there might be an economy based on civic values and solidarity. Adloff justifies this by separating the economy, capitalism and the market from each other. For him, the economy cannot be reduced to the market, and the economy is also related to the social process of production, redistribution and reciprocity. Besides that, a market cannot regulate itself and is in need of political regulation; thus, the principles of civil society and solidarity might come in handy in this situation. An economic enterprise does not have to be capitalist; there are also cooperatives, local producer communities, not-for-profit institutions and other kinds of collective bodies (Adloff, 2021: 153).

However, an attempt to merge a capitalist economy and democratic values of the civil society must be carefully approached. A more realistic approach to the relationship between civil society, democracy and capitalism could be found in Eikenberry and Kluver's (2004) work. For them, marketisation of the public sector could be harmful to democracy and citizenship, and a similar concern is also about the transformation of non-profit organisations. They claim that the marketisation of the non-governmental organisations is about the institutional framework of the

contemporary era. Environmental factors for non-governmental organisations, such as the economy or politics, can be effective in order to push those organisations into embracing market-like methods (Eikenberry and Kluver, 2004: 133). However, this process also brings the risk of deterioration or corruption of the non-governmental organisations in the making and maintaining a powerful civil society. Also, the market does not or very little value the democratic ideals like fairness or justice. And finally, the role of non-governmental organisations in opening up a public space in order to contribute to the learning of democratic citizenship in a neo-Tocquevillian sense is not seen in the process of marketisation (Eikenberry and Kluver, 2004: 138).

A discussion about the relationship between civil society, democracy, and capitalism can be traced back to Alexis de Tocqueville due to his way of theorising civil society. An early trace of this relation can be found in Alexis de Tocqueville's writings, via a reading of the separation between political and economic spheres in capitalism. So that, in order to comprehend this relation, the ideas of Alexis de Tocqueville should be revisited. When the contemporary understanding of civil society and Alexis de Tocqueville's ideas on civil society are brought together, some questions are raised. Among these questions, what were the social conditions in the 19th-century US, where Tocqueville codified his ideas on civil society, and in which way did these conditions affect Tocqueville? Another question is whether there is any continuity between the modern understanding of civil society and the perspective of civil society in the 19th-century central production system.

In this study, it will be argued that the relationship between civil society and the economic sphere is based on civil society's capacity to establish and maintain the political sphere. This function of civil society could be realised through democracy. The relationship between civil society and the economic sphere in 19th-century America can also be found nowadays via this function. On this occasion, the main claim of this article is that the relationship between the concept of civil society and the economic sphere is inevitable, and in order to put forward this claim, it is necessary to revisit the 19th-century political, economic and social relations that led to the formation of Tocqueville's concept of civil society.

In this context, to grasp the understanding of civil society of Alexis de Tocqueville, the economic and social conditions in the 19th century will be presented in relation to his ideas. Later, the entities that constitute the core of Tocqueville's understanding of civil society, which are civil associations, political associations, and the state, will be scrutinised. Finally, with a combined reading of both the social and economic structures of the American 19th century and a Tocquevillian civil society, it will be discussed in what ways Tocqueville's thoughts on civil society correspond to the distinction of a political-economic sphere, which is a distinguishing feature of capitalism (Akbulut, 2005: 160). In general, the paper will argue that the relationship between civil-political associations and the state can be read as not just the development of civil politics but also as a network of complex economic relationships in the thoughts of Alexis de Tocqueville.

Methodology

This study aims to use a social historical perspective, namely, the social history of political thought. To clarify the meaning of historical perspective, in Ellen Wood's words (2009: 26), humanising the ideas by not separating them from their own material and practical environment and by dealing with theorists and their thoughts without losing the humane connection with them. By the same token, '[...] every classic text in political theory, among other things, is an important reflection of its times, telling us much about the nature of its particular society' (Wood, 1978: 345). From this point of view, it should not be forgotten that the thoughts of Alexis de Tocqueville were produced in a particular society at a specific time. In this context, the ideas he brought forward, the systems he developed, and his contributions must not be considered ahistorical, universal or everlasting. In another saying, the thought of Tocqueville must not be pushed to the outside of history. As Uslu said (2017: 133),

political ideas, like all other forms of thought, are part of the social formation and intellectual debate of their period. Therefore, separating the thoughts and the whole milieu where they developed can be seen as a way of separating the thoughts from their meanings.

In this regard, approaching Alexis de Tocqueville and his ideas from a historical perspective offers an alternative reading. In general, although the studies on Alexis de Tocqueville's *Democracy in America* cover various kinds of topics, the way of approaching Alexis de Tocqueville and his own historical moment has mostly been disregarded. The reason behind this choice is an effort to demonstrate that the relationship between the state, civil society, and politics can be evaluated from an economic perspective. A social history could be a valuable understanding of the necessary tools to interpret the links between the state and society and its different aspects, such as economy, politics, or history. In a Tocquevillean context, the methodology provides a profound outlook to realise the relationship between civil-politics and the state, which can be seen as a broader network of relations in the economic sphere. In this sense, the paper will employ the historical perspective as a methodology to argue that, in the thoughts of Alexis de Tocqueville, the separation between civil-political associations and the state coincides with the separation of the political and economic spheres.

Economic and Social Environments in the US during the 19th Century

The 19th century in the United States witnessed a profound transformation in its economic, social, and political landscape, driven mainly by factors such as industrialisation, mechanisation, and, as a result, increased productivity, especially in the field of cotton textile (Allen, 2011: 81–82). These changes created an environment conducive to the growth and development of capitalism, and government support for business growth accelerated the process. This transformation had far-reaching implications for American society, shaping its economic structure, social dynamics, and political institutions.

Industrialisation in the 19th century in the US can be noticed in different ways, such as a drastic change in the numbers of patents for manufacturing and constructing, the construction of railroads, which drew the attention of the federal and local governments by surpassing Europe (Cameron, 1993: 204) and the legal support to the corporatisation process. In the early days of the United States, they made important changes to how businesses were organised. In 1811, New York devised a way for corporations to become official. This ensured the shareholders would not be personally responsible for all the company's problems. They would only be responsible for the money they put into it. The idea behind this regulation, which other states followed with the same or similar steps later, was to make it safer for people to invest in companies and allow companies to get more capital by selling shares (Harreld, 2016: 167). Between 1820 and 1845, the ratio of patents in agriculture, construction, electrical, manufacturing, transportation, and other categories was 73,8%. This was followed by 67,3% in 1846-1865 and 58,9% between 1866-1885 (Khan and Sokoloff, 2004: 400). Although its production mainly was based on agriculture, in the 1860s, the US was the second largest manufacturer after Great Britain in the world (Harreld, 2016: 149).

In the first half of the 19th century, egalitarian sentiments and hostility to special privileges were more substantial in the US than in Europe, where both states and the federal government could establish corporations, and incorporation became a necessity to conduct business in the early 1840s (Cameron, 1993: 214). Not having a non-feudal tradition and trust in the market could be seen as the reason behind the oppositional stance towards individual immunities and the desire for institutionalisation in the US, where the federal government was a supporting agent for the private companies and enterprises to accelerate the development of the national resources (Cameron, 1993: 216).

The numbers from different fields in the 19th-century US can provide a picture of the dimension of industrialisation, which is a crucial aspect of the capitalisation process. According to the realised private production income in 1799, while agriculture was 264 million dollars, manufacturing was just 31 million dollars. These numbers changed dramatically in 1889. While agriculture was 1,517 million dollars, manufacturing became 2,022 million dollars (Bureau of the Census, 1949: 14). Moreover, during the second half of the 19th century, between 1869 and 1879, the average payment in the agricultural sector was 20.5 dollars; this number decreased to 17.1 dollars between 1889 and 1899. At the same time, from 1869 to 1879, the average payment in the manufacturing sector was 13.9 dollars. This number increased to 18.2 dollars between 1889 and 1899 (Bureau of the Census, 1949: 13). This change indicates the growing nature of industrialisation in the US during the 19th century.

The mechanisation process also increased dramatically, between 1820 and 1913, the Gross Stock of Machinery and Equipment Per Capita was up to 87 to 2,749. These increases affected efficiency as well. From 1820 to 1913, capital/output ratios, labour, and total factor productivity increased from 0,07 to 0,52 (Maddison, 2007: 316). By comparing the growth rate in GDP between 1500 and 1820, it can be realised that the sum of the US and Canada is greater than that of the other Western and non-Western countries, which indicates the growth speed of the US before the 19th century.

To sum up, in the 19th century, different but interconnected factors like industrialisation, mechanisation, an increase in productivity, and the support of the federal government for the incorporation process made the American market and sociopolitical milieu compatible with the growth and development of capitalism. Under these circumstances, the process of capitalisation can be expected to be directly or indirectly felt in different areas, such as civil society. The period during which Alexis de Tocqueville wrote down his evaluations towards American civil society is a period where rapid industrialisation and its dynamics are interwoven with an individualistic understanding of the society, which is the core value of American society, according to Tocqueville (2009: 132).

Triangulation of Civil - Political Associations and the State

In the thought of Alexis de Tocqueville, the concept of civil society gains its meaning with his civil association, political association, and (central) state conceptualisations (Woldring, 1998: 372–373). Thus, revealing the connections among the three concepts would be essential in demonstrating Tocqueville's perspective on civil society.

Alexis de Tocqueville's thoughts in the 19th century, especially in the United States, are valuable to understand the roots of modern civil society organisations. Those civil society entities of the time, which helped to keep people together in frontiers where no state existed before, are connected with the locality of American democracy (Brinton, 2010: 454). Rather than being sole and uniform, they exist in a structure separated into three parts: permanent, political, and civil. The permanent ones consist of towns, counties, cities or other kinds of local political and administrative organisations, generally seen as local governments or authorities (Villa, 2006: 224). In this context, for Tocqueville, the local government agents are part of his understanding of civil society. The fundamental separation is not between civil-political society or civil-political associations but between local and central institutions (Villa, 2006: 219).

In this sense, the main antagonism occurred between local and central authorities. The effort of the local communities to counter the central government in the relationship between the state and themselves played an essential role in the process of shaping American society back then. The understanding of a powerful local authority invigorated the anti-state ideas in the USA. In this context, it makes sense that the central state was seen, on one hand, as an evilness born of necessity and, on the other hand, society as a blessing that was originated from the search of the people to fulfil

the needs of their own (Balogh, 2009: 24; Uslu, 2021: 434). Besides, at the time of revolution, the American citizens who were deprived of any status or wealth imagined the fact that they could be equal through institutional associations such as the local governments, counties or churches (Balogh, 2009: 26).

While being apart from the central state, the civil society for Tocqueville consisted of two forms: civil and political associations. The main point that separates them becomes evident in the relationship where they connect with politics. The political associations try to affect politics within political structures, apart from civil associations, which aim to influence politics by standing outside the government or political institutions. According to Alexander (2006: 8), the most crucial feature of the civil associations, which makes them civic, is their nature of civic orientation or, in other words, using communication to affect the public idea. The political associations consist of a political doctrine, thought or worldview shared by people who willingly participate in political action. As an example, political parties, as the largest political associations, aim to rule the state via elections and representation mechanisms.

All the associations are in a struggle to affect the political mechanisms at the local or national level; however, the point where they separate is seen in the method of this struggle to affect. In the political system, local/national assemblies, parties or associations in general, through the institutionalised branches of political participation, can be seen as political associations which aim to be included in political representation mechanisms. In return, the associations that act without being directly involved in political representation mechanisms for purposes related to social and daily life, such as education, infrastructure/superstructure works, religion, social aid or charity organisations, etc., can be called civil associations. Unlike political associations, civil associations reinforce the understanding that people should solve their problems and consolidate the idea of being a society against individualisation or atomization derived from democratic equality. Civil associations provide an identity and a form of recognition against democratic individualism, which breaks down the social structure and the connection between villagers and Kings constituted by the aristocracy (Villa, 2006: 229).

However, at this point, it should be noted that even though there is a distinction between them, the civil and political associations interact. According to Tocqueville (2009: 913), it is rare and requires craftsmanship that comes together with many people physically in civic life. At this moment, politics becomes a way of coming together. Political associations, although there are differences among their members, in the name of subjection of the totality of a particular will into the general will, can get together synchronously. This situation turns the political associations into a school where all the citizens can learn the general theory of coming together for free (de Tocqueville, 2009: 913–914). This schooling function can also be seen as a foundation for a healthy democracy (Encarnación, 2000: 9) and creates a practical and theoretical background to the footsteps in which civil associations rise (Foley and Edwards, 1996: 43).

For Tocqueville (2009: 897), the main reason for creating togetherness in the forms of associations for a common goal on a voluntary basis is the weakness of individualism. This point raises the question of against whom people come together. Tocqueville's possible answer to this question holds an essential place in the distinction between civil association, political association, and central state. The effort to create power, which is the underlying desire of people to come together, is a reaction that demonstrates the state and the risk of becoming a despotic regime. According to Tocqueville (2009: 989), who mentioned the risk of losing independence at a place where there is no right and desire of people to come together for political purposes, the civilisation they have in their daily or civil life might be imperilled and cause disorder. However, it is not the disorder that arises from the conflict of interests and antagonisms in society but the despoticization of the central state, which is supposed to regulate and eliminate this disorder. The despoticization of the state will harm not only

the individual's benefit but also the social benefit. For Tocqueville, the way to prevent this despotic form of the state is by creating and strengthening civil associations (Ertugay, 2005: 56). The existence of civil institutions has a vital position against the monopoly of power in a society.

The relationship and interaction between civil-political associations and the central state become clear at this point. The legal and peaceful grounds that these associations enjoy make sense at this point and give them a chance to be legitimate actors alongside the state. However, claiming that the legitimacy of these associations only comes from the law, legality, and their peaceful structures does not seem to be enough. In a democratic society, where individual strength is diminished due to the equalisation of conditions, people can only influence social and political situations by forming associations through coming together (de Tocqueville, 2009: 901). In other words, the legitimacy of the associations originates from the individuals who build them and their freedom of assembly, in addition to the legality of the associations.

Tocqueville noted that there is a sympathy towards the relationship between civil associations and the central state (2009: 915–916). This is because the associations occupy people through public affairs. Also, he points out that they distract citizens and promote them to the works which cannot be done without public peace or consensus, and because of these structures, the system is protected from a revolution. For Tocqueville (2009: 916), it is easy to see why the businessmen in America at that period did not want to disturb the public peace or destroy the central state, considering the businesses would suffer even with the idea of revolution. For him, it is simple to prove that when focusing on a moment of a nation, political associations corrupt the state and paralyse production. However, in a scenario that addresses the totality of the lives of people, the freedom of organising in political matters plays a role in increasing the peace and prosperity of the citizens (de Tocqueville, 2009: 916). In the short term, political associations corrupt politics and the economy; however, in the long term, they boost both the civil associations and the economy, and in a way, they politically passivise the citizens and contribute to the system (Zaleski, 2008: 263). In other words, political associations can be seen as harmful in the short term, but they can also be seen as beneficial for teaching people how to organise themselves in the long term. At this point, the link between political and economic spheres and civil society and the state can be seen much more clearly. Although civil society, both as civil and political associations, is beneficial in order to maintain a self-functioning society in the eyes of Tocqueville, it is also useful for reproducing and maintaining the separation of political and economic spheres. By creating a place where people do not question the economic relations and ways of appropriation, civil society becomes instrumentalised for the separation of political and economic spheres. The regulatory role of the state here plays a role that ensures the maintenance of these relations in harmony.

Thus, to maintain public order, the state may limit the associations that need a non-restricted ground for functioning well. Although this state's right to intervene can only be used in a social consensus that requires citizens' consent and support, this intervention in the associations may come to mind as a contradiction in the thoughts of Tocqueville. However, when approaching this intervention from the separation of the political and economic spheres, it occurs that there is no contradiction at all.

Between Political and Economic Spheres: Tocqueville's Civil Society

At the core of Tocqueville's conceptualization of civil society is based on associations in civil life which is an area for private interest and economic activities and thus related to a capitalist economy (Ertugay, 2005: 54). A critical point that separated the Tocqueville's understanding of civil society and modern day NGOs is that the area of activity of civil society also includes institutions and organisation that have economic and commercial functions and purposes (Zaleski, 2008: 261). Another aspect of Tocqueville's understanding of civil society becomes apparent when civil society organisations are placed against despotism. For him, people who act according to competition or

individual interest will be much more concerned about social disturbance than an authoritarian state. People's desire for public order will be so much in society that, with Tocqueville's words, at the first moment of turmoil, they will be ready to set aside their freedom. This renunciation of freedom leads to despotism, and the way to prevent this is through civil society (Villa, 2006: 203). In another saying, Tocqueville sees civil society as an actor that can solve problems without the need for a state in a moment of turmoil. The associations have the function to balance between the local and the central against the tendency for centralisation (Brinton, 2010: 455). About centralisation, Woldring (1998: 364) stressed the associations challenging the administrative centralisation, which restricts the freedom and accessibility of associations. In other words, the main objection is not towards a central state but to the enlargement of its influence. In a general context, Tocqueville is searching for the right relationship between the state and civil society to support each other and be acceptable for individual interests, civil society and the state (Balogh, 2009: 456).

At this point, it makes sense that the situation may be seen as a contradiction between civil society and its intervention. The existing relationship between production and consumption can be intervened in civil society by protecting the separation of the political and economic spheres. Civil society, a total composition of different associations, can be restricted by the state to protect society.

Herein, it will be helpful to mention the separation of the political and economic spheres. This separation has emerged with capitalism. Before capitalism, the possession of power had coincided with the possession of military and political power. In a society which does not have the capitalist relation of production, the economic power of the dominant classes is based on the non-economic coercion they have (Wood, 2014: 26). While there is no separation of political and economic spheres in a society without capitalism, the social reality of capitalism is based on both formal and institutional separation of economic coercion and political coercion. Even though capitalism separates the political and economic spheres, they have relationships that complete and obligate each other (Akbulut, 2005: 160). For Wood (2003: 33), with the discovery of the economy, the way of separation of the political and economic spheres coincides with the emptying of the political and social content of capitalism, and as a result, it is beneficial for capitalism.

This differentiation has not only a theoretical context but, at the same time, a practical one. This practical context can be seen in the separation of the political and economic in the class movement of the proletariat. When considering the history of capitalism, it can be seen that some political subjects, like political dominance, labour exploitation or appropriation, turn only into economic subjects. Thus, this makes functional the division of political and economic to defend the capital (Wood, 2003: 34). The means of production, money or goods are not approached as a form of capital directly however, under the circumstance in which the producer and the one who appropriated labor confronts, it is required to convert these into capital. This conversion, or in other words 'primitive accumulation', takes place when the workers who are deprived of any means of production and the owners of the means of production come under the circumstances of the market through a relationship of exchange which is concretised as a contract of employment (Marx, 2011: 687). Just as capital is a transformed form of a social order, the social aspect of the economy necessitates dismantling this social aspect by capitalism, thus isolating the economy. However, this distinction is not absolute. Tocqueville saw this non-absolute distinction, and the state's intervention in the economy was positioned on an obscure line to protect society. The state can intervene in the economy, but conditionally; this intervention must cleanse the inside of the economy from the social and exclude it from the political (Wood, 2003: 36). Wood pointed out this (2003: 36) permeable line between the economic and the political sphere. Political power's involvement in the economic sphere must not have social and political goals. This approach that abstractly comprehends society, which cuts off social production from its history, also demonstrates the production included in the market relations as natural law. In this way, it serves the existing market conditions.

The separation between capitalism and different kinds of production is seen when workers take away ownership of the means of production through the right of free and universal suffrage and participation in politics (Akbulut, 2012: 188). The political sphere does not coerce the workers to sell their labour directly; however, it gains functionality through the continuity of the appropriation and the protection of the ownership. The worker selling their labour originates from the economy, which is formed in the market relations to reach the means of production rather than coercion of the political sphere (Wood, 2012: 19).

The separation of the political and economic spheres imposes upon relations of production and distribution that can only exist in the economic sphere and cannot be realised in non-economic relations. Thus, the forms of appropriation are located exclusively within the economic sphere, and any objection or rebellion from the political to the economic sphere is prevented, which at first sight appears to be a contradiction in Tocqueville's thought due to the long- and short-term functions of political associations, makes sense at this point. While political associations may seem harmful in the short term, they take on the task of producing reasonable subjects in the long term for capitalism, whose objections or revolts will remain only in the political sphere. From this point of view, there is no contradiction. Also, for the same reason, Tocqueville's idea that civil associations occupied people through public affairs, thus distracting them from any kind of uprising, gains meaning at this point. In the economic sphere, any objection against appropriation is excluded, or in other words, it is eliminated by being located in the political sphere. The appropriation of surplus value occurs in the economic sphere through economic means. This keeps the production processes away from working conditions and results in those who appropriate the surplus value holding ownership over the means of production (Wood, 2003: 43).

In this system, the ones who do not have the means of production are not deprived of the freedom of participation or enslaved, nor are they exposed to political coercion. For this reason, they are accepted as 'free'. The idea of freedom at this point, in a broader sense, is related to the relations between people and the absence of any kind of violation from others, while in a strict sense, it is about political participation, choosing the executives, overseeing the government or the legislation (Hayek, 2013: 39–41). In another saying, the one who is able to join the associations, for Tocqueville, is regarded as free; however, via the relationship with the economic dynamics, the pressure under the market conditions does not do any harm to this 'freedom'.

Property and market-dominated workplaces, which are excluded from democratic accountability, do not require capitalist intervention (Akbulut, 2012: 190). This phenomenon leads to the capitalist system dealing with democracy on an idiosyncratic political ground. Democracy is arranged with the minimum effect possible on the areas of market and production (Akbulut, 2012: 190). The control of the owner of the capital in the work field is restored via the exclusion of democracy from the economy. The worker in the workplace and the citizen in the street are not the same person. In the context of Tocqueville, freedom can be seen in the political and social participation through associations, although freedom does not carry any kind of economic welfare.

Conclusion

In a Tocquevillean understanding, civil society is a form of organisation where people come together to carry out public affairs in a very wide range. Those public affairs may include local governments' services, education, infrastructure, health, religious organisations or public security. In a way, even the political parties can be seen by him as a form of civil society organisation, which is a legal way for the people to be heard in the political realm. Because of the idea of this wide range of civil society, Tocqueville's notion of civil society should be considered in its own period. This wide range separates his ideas from the contemporary understanding of civil society.

Considering Alexis de Tocqueville's ideas and the 19th-century USA together, it can be clearly seen that in a growing industrial economy, there was a need to organise the social structure according to a capitalist economic system. In this context, under the extent of civil society, the thoughts of Tocqueville and the American social structure overlap in particular areas. In the process of industrial capitalisation, the relationship established by Americans with civil society has provided the opportunity to meet the needs of the changing social structure in the means of sociocultural, economic and political. Comprehending and fulfilling these needs locally, by and through local people, shows the capacity for responding to capitalism with the understanding of the 19th-century American style of civil society. In light of all of these, it can be said that Alexis de Tocqueville's comprehension of civil society has the potential to complete the distinction of developing American capitalism's political and economic sphere. His concept of civil society plays a crucial role in maintaining the distinction between political and economic spheres by regulating the inside of the political sphere. With the help of civil and political associations, this regulation process sustains the gap or separation between the political and economic spheres. It relocates the political sphere to a distant place from the economic sphere. In conclusion, for Alexis de Tocqueville, the concept of civil society has a feature that reproduces and perpetuates the separation of the political and economic spheres created by capitalism at its emergence. As a result, the relationship between Alexis de Tocqueville and the modern understanding of civil society should be reconsidered because of the different contexts, places, and times of Alexis de Tocqueville's associations and NGOs. The separation between the political and economic realms that manifested itself with the emergence of capitalism is reproduced through civil society both in the 19th century and today.

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